

Separation of Acetothioacetanilide Chelates by Thin-layer Chromatography

TARASANKAR PAL and JYOTIRMOY DAS

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104 (India)

Manuscript received 5 December 1977, revised 7 February 1979, accepted 22 February 1979

The chromatographic behaviour of the chelates of acetothioacetanilide with 11 metal ions, viz. Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Pd(II), Pt(II), Au(III), Fe(III) and Se(IV) have been studied on a thin layer of silica gel using 19 different solvent systems. The best separation was obtained with the alcoholic solvents used viz. methanol, ethanol and *n*-butanol. The R_f values were found to increase with the decrease in the dielectric constant of the alcohol or alcohols mixed with benzene or hydrochloric acid. Solvents with donor properties, e.g., isobutyl methyl ketone showed levelling effect on the R_f values. The useful separations have been listed.

CHELATES of acetothioacetanilide (HATA) with various metal ions¹⁻⁵, particularly the 'soft-acid' or 'border-region' metal ions have been used in analytical determinations. Recently during a course of study of the biodegradation of many of these chelates with various bacteria¹ of wild strain the separation of the chelates present in small amounts was necessary. The efficient resolution of multi-component mixtures of acetylacetonates by multistage fractional procedures such as thin-layer (TLC)⁶⁻⁹, paper (PC)¹⁰, gel and gas-liquid (GLC)^{11,12} chromatographic techniques encouraged us to attempt some of these methods as HATA has a chelating centre, '-CO-CH₂-CS-', very close to β -diketones. The TLC technique was chosen in preference to GLC or PC considering the non-volatility of the chelates, ease in recovery and time factor^{10,13}.

We report here the TLC behaviour of the chelates of HATA with 11 metal ions of the groups Ib, IIb, VI and VIIIb of the periodic table on silica gel using 19 different solvent systems.

Experimental

Metal Chelates :

The metal chelates were prepared from aqueous solutions of the chlorides of copper(II)¹, zinc(II)², mercury(II)³, nickel(II)^{4,5}, cobalt(II)^{4,5}, palladium(II)¹, platinum(II)¹, iron(III)⁴, gold(III)¹ and cadmium sulphate³ as well as sodium selenite³ with the addition of alcoholic solution of HATA at proper pH. The ligand was prepared in the laboratory² and all the metal salts were of A.R. or G.R. grade. The purity of the chelates were checked by thermogravimetric analysis. Stock solutions of the chelates were prepared in chloroform and applied to the plate with the help of a microsyringe.

Preparation of Plates :

A Shandon Southern Unoplan model applicator was employed to coat the 20 × 5 × 0.3 cm plates with silica gel (E. Merck)-water (1 : 1) slurry. The thickness of the layer was controlled by adjusting the gate of the applicator at 0.40 mm.

The plates were dried first at room temperature for 30 min, and then at 100° in a mechanical convection oven and cooled in a desiccator.

Preparation of Solvent Systems :

A total of 19 different solvent systems were prepared from reagent grade chemicals : Benzene (S₁) ; 85% methanol-15% benzene (S₂) ; methanol (S₃) ; ethanol (S₄) ; 95% ethanol-5% benzene (S₅) ; *n*-butanol (S₆) ; 99% *n*-butanol-1% 12 M HCl (S_{7A}) ; 97% *n*-butanol-3% 12 M HCl (S_{7B}) ; *iso*-butylmethyl ketone (S₈) ; 95% *iso*-butylmethyl ketone-5% CCl₄ (S₉) ; acetone (S₁₀) ; 90% acetone-10% benzene (S_{11A}) ; 75% acetone-25% benzene (S_{11B}) ; chloroform (S₁₂) ; 82% chloroform-9% benzene-9% pyridine (S_{14A}) ; 71% chloroform-22% benzene-7% pyridine (S_{14B}) ; 61% water-32% acetone-7% pyridine (S₁₅) ; 85% water-15% pyridine (S₁₆), the concentrations are expressed by volume. The basis of the choice of the solvent systems were the solubility of the chelates and the variation in the dielectric constants.

Detection :

The chromatographic tank containing 100 ml of the solvent was allowed to equilibrate for 1 hr and the conventional ascending technique was adopted. The run was always allowed to a constant height of 12 cm. The spots of the chelates could be followed visually as all of them were of self-indicating colour.

However, the plates were developed in an iodine-chamber when spots with various shades of brown were observed : light brown (Zn, Cd), dirty brown (Hg), brown (Fe, Pd), deep brown (Pt, Au, Cu), yellow-brown (Se, Ni) and greenish-yellow (Co).

Other conventional spraying agents like KI solution (0.1M), ammonia (3M), dimethyl glyoxime (1% in 95 ethanol), 8-hydroxyquinoline (0.5% in 60% ethanol), KSCN solution (5%), Na₂S₂O₃ solution (5%) and SnCl₂ solution (in 5M HCl) were of limited use as the HATA chelates were very stable. Dimethyl glyoxime gave spots with nickel (pink), cobalt (deep brown) and copper (light brown), KSCN gave yellow spot with cadmium, aqueous ammonia gave deep brown spots with copper and gold while the spots of copper, palladium and gold with SnCl₂ were brown.

The R_f-values given in Table 1 are from three runs with individual chelates and several runs of multicomponent mixtures. The R_f-value of each chelate was constant for a definite solvent system excepting for Cu(ATA) with acetone benzene (90 : 10) showing a variation of ±1.2% in 5 runs.

Quantitative Estimation :

All the complexes were extracted quantitatively with chloroform from silica gel chromatograms for colorimetric determination¹⁵. The metals (λ_{max} in parantheses) estimated following standard procedures are : Se²⁺ (410 nm), Fe³⁺ (500 nm), Co²⁺ (625 nm), Ni²⁺ (496 nm) and Pt²⁺ (405 nm).

Discussion

All the chelates are of inner metallic type having zero order, so that organic solvents are to be used.

The chelates are also kinetically inert moving like organic inert compounds without leaving any metal ions as tailing unlike some Co(III) and Cu(II) chelates with EDTA¹⁶. The tailing mentioned in Table 1 are of the chelates as the colour after development was the same as that of the corresponding spots. Blank experiments with metal ions were also performed. The R_f-values remained the same in mixtures of metal chelates.

The R_f-values of the free HATA for different solvent systems were also determined under identical conditions. The spots on development in iodine chamber were brown or greenish brown and the R_f-values were distinctly different from the chelates. For example, the R_f-values of HATA with benzene (0.66) and methanol (0.55) were at least 0.04 units apart from the nearest spots for chelates.

None of the chelates moves in water-pyridine system with or without acetone (S_{1.5}, S_{1.6}). Chloroform-benzene-pyridine mixtures (S_{1.4A,B}) are similarly unsuitable for Zn, Cd and Hg chelates, though Ni and Pd give well separated good spots. The spots for Fe, Co and Se are good but too close. Benzene is a good solvent for Zn, Cd, Fe, Ni and Cu chelates though Hg, Pt and Au remain at the start.

The best separations with good spots are obtained using pure alcohols. Methanol, with the highest dielectric constant (d.e.c.) among the three alcohols gives good spots with all the chelates excepting Se (tailing) and Cu(elliptical spot). The R_f-values increase steadily as the d.e.c. decreased, methanol>ethanol>butanol. The same trend has been noticed when the d.e.c. of the alcohols are reduced by mixing benzene (S-2 and S-5). When the d.e.c. is increased by mixing HCl (S_{7.4,B}) tailing occurs. The extent of tailing increases with the

TABLE 1—R_f-VALUES OF METAL-ACETOTHIOACETANILIDE CHELATES*

Solvent System	Zn	Cd	Hg	Se	Fe	Co	Ni	Pd	Pt	Au	Cu
S ₁	0.50	0.54	X	T	0.71-0.66	X	0.76-0.73	T	X	X	0.70
S ₂	0.81	0.75-0.70	X	0.51-0.47	0.70	0.76	0.74	T	T	0.75-0.71	0.81-0.88
S ₃	0.63	0.59	X	T	0.47	0.39	0.44	0.68	0.74	0.59	0.88-0.95
S ₄	0.65	0.64	X	0.60-0.57	0.63	0.66	0.66	T	T	T	0.77-0.73
S ₅	0.66	0.65	X	0.59	0.63	0.66	0.66	T	T	T	T
S ₆	0.69	0.76	X	0.61-0.58	0.90	0.94	0.92	0.93-0.90	0.90-0.87	t	T
S ₇	0.89-0.84	0.87-0.81	0.04-0	0.92-0.81	0.94-0.91	0.96-0.93	0.92-0.89	0.93-0.90	T	0.90-0.82	0.90-0.87
S ₁₀	0.81-0.78	0.72-0.68	X	0.81-0.72	0.82-0.72	0.89-0.78	0.76-0.68	T	T	T	0.83-0.79
S _{11A}	0.81-0.78	0.71-0.68	X	0.62-0.54	0.78-0.68	0.81-0.72	0.79-0.70	T	T	T	0.86-0.83
S _{11B}	0.84	0.89	0.02	0.84	0.93-0.84	0.92-0.81	0.92-0.83	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.12-0.09
S ₁₂	0.45	X	X	0.72	X	X	0.84	0.81	X	X	X
S ₁₃	t	t	X	0.32	T	X	0.56	0.53	X	X	T
S _{14A}	X	X	X	0.91	0.91	0.91-0.83	0.89	0.93	T	T	T
S _{14B}	X	X	X	0.92-0.80	T	T	0.82-0.78	0.82-0.79	t	T	T

* Values given for good spots with leading part (R_L) and tail part (R_T) was less than 2 mm. Otherwise the limits are given.

T—long tail, t—short tail, X—no run.

TABLE 2—SOLVENT SYSTEMS FOR EFFECTIVE SEPARATION OF ACETOTHIOACETANILIDE CHELATES

Solvent System	Metal chelates separated*
S ₁	Ni(0.75) or Fe(0.70) from Zn(0.50) or Cd(0.54) and Hg(x) or Co(x).
S ₂	Zn(0.81) from Fe(0.70) or Co(0.76) or Ni(0.74) ; Cu(0.30) and Hg(x).
S ₃	Pt(0.74) from Pd(0.68) ; Zn(0.63) or Au(0.59) or Cd(0.59) ; Fe(0.47) ; Ni(0.41) or Co(0.39) and Hg(x).
S ₄	Cd(0.76) from Zn(0.69) or Co(0.66) or Ni(0.66) or Fe(0.63) ; Se(0.59) and Hg(x).
S ₅	Fe(0.90), Co(0.94), Ni(0.92), Pd(0.92) or Pt (0.89) from Cd(0.76) ; Zn(0.69) and Hg(x).
S ₁₀	Zn(0.80) from Cd(0.71) and Hg(x).
S _{11A}	Cu(0.82) or Zn(0.80) from Cd(0.70) and Hg(x).
S _{11B}	Pt(1.00), Pd(1.00 , or Au(1.00) from Cu(0.85), Zn(0.84) or Cd(0.89) and Hg(0.02).
S ₁₂	Ni(0.84) or Pd(0.81) from Se(0.72) ; Zn(0.45) and Cd(x) or Hg(x).
S ₁₃	Ni(0.56) or Pd(0.53) from Se(0.32) and Pt(x), Au(x) or Hg(x).

* R_f-values are given in the parenthesis, x—no run.

amount of HCl. The only solvent used having atomic groupings with electron donors, viz. isobutyl methyl ketone gives stretched spots with all the chelates with R_f-values between 0.86 and 0.95. The levelling effect was probably due to some interaction with the solvent.

Mercury(II) chelate behaves most sluggishly in its movement in almost all the solvents, while Fe, Co, Ni generally move close together. The suitable solvent systems for different multicomponent mixtures are summarised in Table 2, which will indicate the usefulness of this study.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for awarding a fellowship to T. Pal.

References

1. T. PAL and J. DAS, Ph.D. Dissertation, Bardwan University, 1978.
2. T. PAL and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 1154.
3. T. PAL and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, *Communicated paper* (1977).
4. K. DUTTA and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1026.
5. K. DUTTA and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **55**, 90.
6. Y. TSUNODA, T. TAKEUCHI and Y. YOSHINO, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1964, **85**, 275.
7. J. C. TREHAN, *Chromatographia*, 1969, **2**, 17.
8. A. I. SUBBOTINA, E. V. IVANOVA and G. A. DOMRACHEV, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1968, **38**, 30.
9. E. W. BERG and J. E. STRASSNER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 127.
10. N. M. KARAYANNIS and A. H. CORWIN, *J. Chromatogr. Sci.*, 1970, **8**, 251.
11. C. A. BURGETT, *J. Chromatogr. Sci.*, 1973, **11**, 611.
12. F. D. HOUGHTON, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1966, **24**, 494.
13. G. BARNIKOW, H. KUNZEK and D. RICHTER, *Ann. Chem.*, 1966, **49**, 695.
14. Z. SOLJIC, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1971, **61**, 390.
15. J. L. SWAIN and J. L. SUDMEIER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, **40**, 418.
16. L. F. DRUDING and R. B. HAGEL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1966, **38**, 478.